

A Fuller Census of Distant Weak AGN via Variability in the CANDELS/Wide Fields

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Overview

The CANDELS *HST* Multi-cycle Treasury Program (Grogin et al. 2011; Koekemoer et al. 2011) includes observations of three “Wide” fields: portions of UKIDSS Ultra Deep Survey (UDS) field in 2010-2011; the Extended Groth Strip (EGS) field in 2011 and 2013; and the COSMOS field in 2011-2012.

In total, CANDELS Wide comprises WFC3/IR exposures in *J* and *H* across 585 arcmin² (EGS portion shown in background mosaic to left) and coordinated parallel ACS/WFC exposures in *V* and *I* across 750-arcmin² that largely overlap the WFC3/IR coverage. The ACS/WFC augments prior COSMOS *I* (2003) and EGS *V* and *I* (2004-2005; right mosaic). No prior ACS/WFC imaging existed within the CANDELS UDS field.

CANDELS Wide observing campaigns were split between two epochs with 52-day spacing for the primary purpose of high-redshift (*z*) supernovae (SNe) detection and follow-up. This combination of sensitivity, high resolution, and time-spacing is also well-suited to detect optical and near-infrared variables (“ONIVs”) among many moderate-*z* galactic nuclei on rest-frame time-scales from weeks to years. We investigate 20506 galactic nuclei to $H_{AB} \approx 25.4$ mag, including 11152 with overlapping optical coverage to $I_{AB} \approx 26$ mag.

Motivation

Prior investigations of multi-epoch deep *HST* imaging to detect optical variability have revealed sizeable populations of distant low-luminosity active galaxies that are largely undetected in even the most sensitive X-ray surveys by *Chandra* in the GOODS-North and South fields (Sarajedini et al 2000, 2003, 2011; Villforth et al. 2010). This study is the first large-scale *HST* variability search into the near-IR, with WFC3.

The overwhelming majority of these ONIVs will be AGN; the small fraction arising from SNe have already been meticulously culled by the CANDELS high-*z* SNe search effort. The ONIVs potentially represent a significant addition to the census of distant AGN subject to multi-wavelength scrutiny with CANDELS, in a fields with a wealth of spectroscopic coverage (e.g., DEEP2/DEEP3).

Methodology

To optimize the signal-to-noise of unresolved variability at the cores of galaxies, we employ PSF-weighted aperture photometry. This minimizes the contamination by the (non-variable) host galaxy. We limit our variability analysis to *I*-band and *H*-band, selecting those sources with $S/N \geq 20$ in a pair of epochs (see plots at lower left). We include the original 2004-2005 EGS ACS/WFC imaging in this analysis, for *I*-band variability baselines up to 9 years.

High-S/N galactic nuclei (away from the stellar locus) that show exceptional variability between any two epochs in *I*-band (F814W) or *H*-band (F160W) are flagged for scrutiny (see plots at lower center). We visually inspect the ONIV candidates to reject any spurious sources due to various image artifacts (e.g., survey boundaries, diffraction spikes, WFC3 persistence and “death-star” feature, etc.). Our remaining sample of ONIVs from all three CANDELS Wide fields comprises 133 *I*-band and 132 *H*-band variables, largely non-overlapping.

CANDELS/EGS
WFC3 J&H Mosaic

AEGIS
ACS V&I Mosaic

Census & Properties:

UDS Field: 39 I-band & 45 H-band variables

- low spec-*z* completeness, but includes $z_{spec} = 4.08$
- Few matches to *XMM* (100ksec) or to *Spitzer* IRPLGs

COSMOS Field: 54 I-band & 55 H-band variables

- 13 matches to zCOSMOS-Deep, with $z_{spec} \leq 3.08$
- <5% detected by shallow *XMM* & *Chandra* imaging

EGS Field: 40 I-band & 32 H-band variables

- DEEP2/DEEP3 includes 45 of 72, with $z_{spec} \leq 3.48$
- <10% detected at $L_X > 10^{42}$ by *Chandra* 800ks imaging

Above, we plot the *H*-band mag versus redshift for the ONIVs. Spec-*z* completeness for these faint galaxies currently ranges from ~50% in the EGS field (DEEP2;DEEP3) down to 10% in the UDS field: Most ONIVs are bright enough for a robust *VJH* phot-*z*, but these estimates are vastly improved with 3D-HST grism data (lower right).

Chandra stacking of COSMOS-field ONIVs reveals a modest (1.5 σ) excess of 2-8 keV X-rays, implying a weak AGN luminosity of $L_X \approx 10^{41.8}$ if $z \approx 1$ sources.

